

New records of Glaphyridae (Col., Scarabaeoidea) from Iran

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Abstract

New distributional data are given for 27 species of Iranian Glaphyridae. Two of them, *Glaphyrus calvaster* Zaitzev, 1923, and *Pygopleurus transcaucasicus* (Petrovitz, 1962), are recorded from Iran for the first time. Further data on Glaphyridae species and their status in Iran is provided.

Keywords: New record, *Glaphyrus*, *Eulasia*, *Pygopleurus*, Iran.

چکیده

گزارش‌های جدید از فون سوسک‌های خانواده (Col. Scarabaeoidea) Glaphyridae از ایران
اولیویه مونتروی

در این مقاله اطلاعات جدیدی از پراکنش ۲۷ گونه از خانواده Glaphyridae ارائه شده است. دو گونه *Glaphyrus calvaster* Zaitsev, 1923 و *Pygopleurus transcaucasicus* (Petrovitz, 1962) برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شوند.
واژگان کلیدی: گزارش جدید، *Eulasia*, *Pygopleurus* و ایران

Introduction

The family Glaphyridae is represented by about 250 species in the New World, Palaearctic and Oriental regions (Hawkins, 2006; Smith, 2009; Nikodým & Bezd k, 2016). It is highly diversified in Western Palaearctic area, especially around the Mediterranean Basin and in the Middle East region. Glaphyridae is known in Iran by about 50 species (Nikodým & Bezd k, 2016) within the three genera *Glaphyrus* Latreille, 1802, *Pygopleurus* Motschulsky, 1860, and *Eulasia* Truqui, 1848. Despite recent studies on this family in Iran (Baraud, 1989, 1990; Nikodým & Král, 1998; Mitter, 2001; Montreuil & Serri, 2007; Nikodým & Keith, 2007; Keith & Uliana, 2008; Uliana & Sabatinelli, 2010), the distribution of most Iranian species remains poorly known. The study of new material led to new finding for 27 species of which two species are recorded here from Iran for the first time.

Material and Methods

The beetle specimens for this study were mainly collected personally between 2002 and 2015 in the course of several field trips with the researchers of the Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection and Iranian Forests and Rangelands Research Institute. Extra material housed in different collections were examined through this study which are as follows:

CDK: Denis Keith collection (Chartres, France)

COM: Olivier Montreuil collection (Fleury-les-Aubrais, France)

HMIM: Hayk Mirzayans Insects Museum, Insect Taxonomy Research Department, Iranian Research Institute of Plant Protection (Tehran, Iran)

MNHN: Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (Paris, France)

The distribution of each species in Iran is from the data and citations in the text. The distribution out of Iran for *Eulasia*, *Pygopleurus* and *Glaphyrus* is given after Baraud (1989, 1990) and Nikodým & Keith (2007) respectively.

Results

Eulasia (s. str.) *aurantiaca* (Reitter, 1890)

Material examined. Iran – Lorestan: Dahriz, 1880 m, 31.V.2007 (COM).– **Kordestan:** Sanandaj, 18.V.1951 (HMIM).– **Kermanshah:** Kermanshah, 22.V.1951 (HMIM).– **Hamedan:** Tuyserkan, Velashjerd, 13.V.1997 (HMIM); Shahrestaneh, 02.VI.2007 (COM).– **Azerbaijan-e Gharbi:** Rezaieh [Urmia], Kuh-e Silvaneh, 24.VI.1970 (HMIM); Sevan, 50 km NW Urmia, 09.VI.1999 (CDK); 5 km Bukan, 1780 m, 26.IV.2001 (CDK); Takht-e Soleyman, 2400 m, 09.VI.2000 (CDK).

Remarks. *Eulasia aurantiaca* was described from Kordestan. Baraud (1990) recorded it from Kermanshah.

Distribution. Northwestern Iran. Eastern

Turkey (Baraud, 1990).

Eulasia (s. str.) azerbaijanica (Petrovitz, 1980)

Material examined. Iran – Gilan: Piri Valley, 500 m, 12.VI.2002 (COM); Damash, 1800 m, 13.VI.2002 (COM); Rudbar, 18.V.1967 (HMIM).– Tehran: Damavand, 13.V.1967 (HMIM); Nessa, 2200 m, 02.VII.1999 (CDK); Tehran, 09.V.1985 (HMIM).– Alborz: Siahchal, 27.V.2011 (COM), 25.V.2015 (COM); Karaj, Shahrestanak, Sarak, 31.V.1991 (HMIM).– Ghazvin: Ghostinlar, 28.V.2011 (COM); Ghazvin, 20.V.1991 (HMIM); Zidasht, 22.V.2012 (COM).– Zanjan: 5 km N. Zanjan, 21.V.2008 (COM); Zanjan, 31.V.1971 (HMIM); Alamut, Gazorkhan, 21.VI.1995 (HMIM); Taham, 20.V.2008 (COM); Meydanak, 20.V.2008 (COM).– Azerbaijan-e Gharbi: Miandoab, 20.V.1975 (HMIM).

Remarks. This species was described from Azerbaijan-e Sharghi (Tabriz). It is endemic to Iran.

Distribution. Northwestern Iran.

Eulasia (s. str.) bodemeyeri (Petrovitz, 1965)

Material examined. Iran – Alborz: Siahchal, 27.V.2011 (COM), 25.V.2015 (COM).– Hamedan: Aberomand, 01.VI.2007 (COM); Shahrestaneh, 02.VI.2007 (COM).– Zanjan: Ghareh Poshtloo, 20.V.2008 (COM); Taham, 20.V.2008 (COM); 5 km N. Zanjan, 21.V.2008 (COM); Meydanak, 20.V.2008 (COM).– Kerman: Darun, V.1960 (MNHN).– Esfahan: Damaneh, 31.V.2004 (HMIM).– Fars: Beyza, 15.V.1952 (HMIM); Eghlid, 03.VI.1969 (HMIM).

Remarks. This species was described from Lorestan. Baraud (1990) recorded it from Tehran and Esfahan.

Distribution. Southern and central Iran.

Eulasia (s. str.) bombylifomis (Pallas, 1871)

Material examined. Iran – Ardabil: Moghan, 20.VIII.1968 (HMIM), 15.VI.1969 (HMIM).– Mazandaran: Shahpasand, 20.V.1956 (HMIM) – Golestan: Gorgan, Golidagh, 01.V.1958 (HMIM), 14.V.1959 (HMIM); PM Golestan, Khajenarenj, 1350 m, 04.V.1999 (HMIM).– Khorasan-e Razavi: Mashad, 17.V.1949 (HMIM).

Remarks. Baraud (1968) and Modarres Awal (2006) recorded this species from Azerbaijan-e Sharghi and Khorasan respectively.

Distribution. Northern Iran. Southern Russia,

Caucasus, Turkmenistan (Baraud, 1990).

Eulasia (s. str.) chrysopyga (Faldermann, 1835)

Material examined. Iran – Azerbaijan-e Sharghi: Arasbaran, 1980 m, 25.VI.2002 (COM); Kaleybar, Ghale Babak, 2100 m, 05.VII.1997 (HMIM), 23.VI.2002 (COM); Ahar, 15.VI.1967 (HMIM); Kaleybar, (1700 m), 22.VI.2002 (COM); Kaleybar, Vayeghan, 06.VIII.1992 (HMIM); Kaleybar, Youzband, 04.VII.1997 (HMIM); Asheghloo-Makidi road, 38°53'42"N 46°48'54"E, 1850 m, 24.VI.2015 (COM); Marzrud, Kalan station, 38°46'00"N 46°48'11"E, 2550 m, 25.VI.2015 (COM).– Ardabil: Khalkhal, pass, 2100 m, 25.VI.2002 (COM); Moghan, Pirlar, 07.VI.1978 (HMIM).– Gilan: Astara-Ardabil road, 1000 m, 25.V.1999 (COM).

Distribution. Northwestern Iran. Turkey, Caucasus.

Eulasia (s. str.) nitidicollis (Reiche, 1862)

Material examined. Iran – Kermanshah: Kermanshah, 22.V.1951 (HMIM), 23.V.1951 (HMIM), 29.V.1951 (HMIM); Ghasr-e Shirin, 05.1950 (HMIM); Ghasr-e Shirin, Sarpol-e Zahab, 12.VI.1951 (HMIM); Bidsorkh, 1790 m, 21.V.2007 (COM); Bigrezai, 1530 m, 23.V.2007 (COM); Jalilvand, 23.V.2007 (COM); Khosravi, 12.IV.1951 (HMIM); Naft Chah, 22.IV.1950 (HMIM), 25.IV.1956 (HMIM); Zhamerg, 29.V.2007 (COM); Chaharzebar-e Olya, 17.V.1997 (HMIM).– Khuzestan: Izeh, Susan, 600 m, 26.IV.1995 (HMIM); Masjed Soleyman, 07.V.1969 (HMIM).– Ilam: Mehran, 12.IV.1948 (HMIM); Ilam, 09.V.1953 (HMIM).– Hamedan: Aberomand, 01.VI.2007 (COM); Khariz Salahedin, 01.VI.2007 (COM); Tuyserkhan, Velashjerd, 13.V.1997 (HMIM).– Fars: Shiraz, 10.IV.1980 (HMIM).– Kordestan: 13.V.1959 (HMIM).

Remarks. Zairi (1976) recorded this species from Fars.

Distribution. Western and Central Iran. Turkey, Syria, Jordan.

Eulasia (s. str.) carinata Baraud, 1990

Material examined. Iran – Kermanshah: Ghasr-e Shirin, 11.IV.1951 (HMIM).

Remarks. This species was described from Kermanshah (Beni Laan). It is endemic to Iran.

Distribution. Southwestern Iran.

***Eulasia (s. str.) naviauxi* Baraud, 1971**

Material examined. Iran – **Fars:** Eghlid, 03.VI.1969 (HMIM); Dasht Arjan, Zanganeh, 2200 m, 04-05.VI.1968 (HMIM); Beyza, IV.1952 (HMIM), 23.IV.1952 (HMIM), 15.V.1952 (HMIM), 30.V.1952 (HMIM).– **Sistan va Baluchestan:** Sekouh-e Zabol, 26.IV.1950 (HMIM).

Remarks. This species was described from Fars (Shiraz). Nikodým & Král (1998) recorded it from Fars. It is endemic to Iran.

Distribution. Southeastern Iran.

***Eulasia (Rudeulasia) chalybaea* (Faldermann, 1835)**

Material examined. Iran – **Zanjan:** Ghareh Poshtloo, 20.V.2008 (COM).– **Ghazvin:** Ghazvin, 25.V.1949 (HMIM), 10.VI.1949 (HMIM), 20.V.1991 (HMIM), 22.V.2012 (COM).– **Tehran:** Evin, 04.V.1970 (HMIM), 28.V.1971 (HMIM), 03.VI.1971 (HMIM).– **Hamedan:** Aberomand, 01.VI.2007 (COM); Serkan, Korzan, 02.VI.2007 (COM); Shahrestaneh, 02.VI.2007 (COM).– **Markazi:** Saveh, 05.VI.1972 (HMIM).– **Kermanshah:** Kermanshah, 22–23.V.1951 (HMIM).– **Ilam:** Ilam, 24–25.V.1950 (HMIM).– **Kordestan:** 12.V.1946 (HMIM).

Remarks. Baraud (1968) recorded this species from Azerbaijan-e Sharghi.

Distribution. Western Iran. Transcaucasus, Armenia.

***Eulasia (Rudeulasia) pulchra* ssp. *kurdistana* (Petrovitz, 1968)**

Material examined. Iran – **Ghazvin:** Razdjerd, 06.VI.2011 (COM).– **Hamedan:** Aberomand, 01.VI.2007 (COM); Hamedan, 28.VI.2000 (HMIM); Tuyserkan, 1966 (HMIM); Kartil Abad, 31.V.2007 (COM).– **Kermanshah:** Jalilvand, 23.V.2007 (COM); Paveh, 28.V.2007 (COM); Zhamerg, 29.V.2007 (COM); Sarmiel, 24.V.2007 (COM); Kermanshah, 23.V.1951 (HMIM).– **Ilam:** Ilam, 25.V.1950 (HMIM), 03.V.1953 (HMIM).– **Kordestan:** 12.V.1946 (HMIM).– **Kerman:** Jiroft, 10.VII.1974 (HMIM).

Distribution. Western and southern Iran. Eastern Turkey.

***Eulasia (Rudeulasia) straussi* (Ganglbauer, 1905)**

Material examined. Iran – **Azerbaijan-e Gharbi:** 3 km E Bukan, 1780 m, 26.IV.2001 (CDK). – **Hamedan:** Gyan, 31.V.2007 (COM); Kartil Abad, 31.V.2007 (COM); Khariz Salahedin, 01.VI.2007

(COM); Tuyserkan, Velashjerd, 13.V.1997 (HMIM); Samen, 31.V.2007 (COM).– **Kermanshah:** Javanrud, Aziz Abad, 29.V.2007 (COM); Ghasr-e Shirin, 19.IV.1951 (HMIM); Ghasr-e Shirin, Sarpol-e Zahab, 12.VI.1951 (HMIM); Khosravi, 12.IV.1951 (HMIM); Kermanshah, 22.V.1951 (HMIM).– **Lorestan:** Babazeyd-Shah Abad, 920 m, 04.V.1976 (HMIM); 90 km S Khoram Abad, 23.IV.1976 (HMIM); Dorud, Papiun, 02.VI.2004 (HMIM).

Remarks. This species was described from Iran. Nikodým & Král (1998) recorded it from Lorestan.

Distribution. Southwestern Iran. Iraq, Eastern Turkey.

***Eulasia (Trichopleurus) vittata* ssp. *persica* Petrovitz, 1963**

Material examined. Iran – **Kermanshah:** Kerend, V.1951 (HMIM); Javanrud, Ali Abad, 29.V.2007 (COM); Javanrud, Aziz Abad, 29.V.2007 (COM); Ghasr-e Shirin, 12.VI.1951 (HMIM); Ghasr-e Shirin, Dalakou, 13.V.1951 (HMIM); Ghasr-e Shirin, Sarpol-e Zahab, 10.IV.1951 (HMIM), 12.V.1951 (HMIM); Komedareh, 28.V.2007 (COM); Rijab, 25.V.2007 (COM); Rijab, Sarabeskandar, 22.VI.1968 (HMIM).– **Ghazvin:** Razdjerd, 06.VI.2011 (COM).– **Hamedan:** Darreh-e Moradbeyg, 2350 m, 05-06.VII.1998 (HMIM); Serkan, Korzan, 02.VI.2007 (COM).– **Zanjan:** 5 km N. Zanjan, 21.V.2008 (COM); Armaghankhaneh, Mari, 36°59'52"N 48°28'39"E, 2380 m, 20.VI.2015 (COM).– **Azerbaijan-e Gharbi:** Sendji, 15.VI.1970 (HMIM); Shapur, 06.VII.2000 (HMIM).– **Azerbaijan-e Sharghi:** Ghooshchi, 20.VI.1970 (HMIM).– **Kordestan:** Bidjar Garus, Chang-Almas, Hassanteimur, 2200-2500 m, 08.VII.1968 (HMIM); Sanadadj, Ariz, 2200 m, 05.VII.1972 (HMIM); Marivan, 23.VI.2002 (HMIM).– **Esfahan:** Golpayegan, 2200–2800 m, 27.VI.1969 (HMIM); Khonsar, 02.VII.1969 (HMIM).

Remarks. This subspecies was described from Iran. It is endemic to this country.

Distribution. Western and southwestern Iran.

***Pygopleurus anahitae* Mitter, 2001**

Material examined. Iran – **Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad:** Yasuj, Tolegorgi, 2000 m, 04.V.1985 (HMIM).– **Fars:** Firuza Abad, Afrar, 10.IV.1953 (HMIM).

This species was described from Mahabad

(Azarbaijan-e Gharbi). Keith & Uliana (2008) recorded it from Kordestan and Lorestan. It is endemic to Iran.

Distribution. Southwestern Iran.

***Pygopleurus banghaasi* (Reitter, 1895)**

Material examined. Iran – Golestan: Almehr, 1600 m, 24.IV.1997 (HMIM); Gonbad, 26.IV.1956 (HMIM), 26.IV.1958 (HMIM); Golidagh, 09.V.1958 (HMIM), 05.V.1967 (HMIM); Narlidagh, 08.V.1967 (HMIM); Yekechenar, 06.V.1967 (HMIM).

Remarks. Baraud (1968) and Mitter (2001) recorded this species from Mazandaran and Khorasan respectively.

Distribution. Northeastern Iran. Turkmenistan.

***Pygopleurus cyaneoviolaceus* Motschulsky, 1859**

Material examined. Iran – Gilan: Damash, 1800 m, 13.VI.2002 (COM).– Ardabil: Heyran, 1700 m, 19.VI.2002 (COM), 1600 m, 18.VI.2002 (COM); Kelishom, 2100 m, 03.V.2000 (CDK).

Distribution. Northwestern Iran. Caucasus, Azerbaijan.

***Pygopleurus cyanescens* (Reitter, 1890)**

Material examined. Iran – Ghazvin: Ghostinlar, 20.V.2011 (COM); Ghazvin, 10.VI.1949 (HMIM), 15.VI.1949 (HMIM), 20.VI.1949 (HMIM); Agha Baba, 06.1948 (HMIM).– Azerbaijan-e Sharghi: 12 km NW Marand, 06.VII.2000 (HMIM); 44 km SW Tabriz, 15.VI.2000 (HMIM).– Hamedan: Serkan, Korzan, 02.VI.2007 (COM); Gyan, 31.V.2007 (HMIM); Aberomand, 01.VI.2007 (COM); Hamedan (HMIM).– Kermanshah: Kermanshah, 23.V.1951 (HMIM); Jalilvand, 23.V.2007 (HMIM); Kartil Abad, 31.V.2007 (HMIM); Rijab, 25.V.2007 (COM); Zhamerg, 29.V.2007 (COM); Ghasr-e Shirin, 24.III.1951 (HMIM).

Remarks. Baraud (1968) and Nikodým & Král (1998) recorded this species from Azerbaijan-e Gharbi, and Zanzan respectively.

Distribution. Western Iran. Syria, Southern and Eastern Turkey, Caucasus, Armenia.

***Pygopleurus distinctus* (Faldemann, 1835)**

Material examined. Iran – Ilam: Ilam, 09.V.1953 (HMIM).

Distribution. Southwestern Iran. Southeastern Turkey.

***Pygopleurus psilotrichius* (Faldemann, 1835)**

Material examined. Iran – Golestan:

Gonbad-e Kavus, V.1950 (HMIM), 30.IV.1965 (HMIM), 23.VI.1969 (HMIM); Karim Ishan, 500 m, 2-5.IV.2001 (CDK); Gonbad-e Kavus, Gharabalkhan, 30.IV.1963 (HMIM); Maraveh Tappeh, Kheshtly, 26.IV.1997 (HMIM); Maraveh Tappeh, Kalaleh, 26.IV.1997 (HMIM); Gorgan, Galikesh, 25.IV.1974 (HMIM); Ramian-Gorgan, 15.VI.1948 (HMIM); Gorgan, Golidagh, 20.V.1956 (HMIM), 15.V.1959 (HMIM); Yekechenar, 06.V.1967 (HMIM).– Mazandaran: Behshahr, 09.V.1956 (HMIM), 11.V.1967 (HMIM).– Zanzan: 30 km NE Zanzan, 16.V.2001 (CDK).– Ardabil: Baran, 02.V.1961 (HMIM).– Azerbaijan-e Gharbi: Pasveh, 1600 m, 06.V.2000 (CDK).– Kordestan: 3 km Morad Abad, 2200 m, 28.IV.2001 (CDK).

Remarks. Baraud (1968), Nikodým & Král (1998) and Modarres Awal (2006) recorded this species from several provinces in northern Iran.

Distribution. Northern Iran. Southern and eastern Turkey, Jordan, Caucasus, Armenia, Turkmenistan.

***Pygopleurus transcaucasicus* (Petrovitz, 1962)**

Material examined. Iran – Azerbaijan-e

Sharghi: Kaleybar, 1700 m, 21.VI.2002 (COM).– Ardabil: Dudjagh, 28.V.1968 (HMIM).

Distribution. New to Iran. Caucasus.

***Glaphyrus* (s. str.) *laufferi* Reitter, 1903**

Material examined. Iran – Sistan va

Baluchestan: Bampur, 07.VI.1947 (HMIM).– Khuzestan: Behbahan, 01.V.1968 (HMIM).– Fars: Kazerun, V.1953 (HMIM); Saadat Abad, 26.V.1969 (MNHN).

Remarks. This species was described from Bakhtiyari. It is endemic to Iran.

Distribution. Southern Iran.

***Glaphyrus* (s. str.) *luristanus* Reitter, 1903**

Material examined. Iran – Tehran: Kamard,

02.VI.2012 (COM); Damavand, 19.VI.1949 (HMIM).– Alborz: Taleghan, Takieh, 30.VI.2007 (COM); Taleghan, Mehran, 30.VI.2007 (COM); Taleghan dam, 1650 m, 18.VI.1992 (HMIM).– Ghazvin: Ghazvin 20.V.1948 (HMIM).– Zanzan: Yukharichay, 1660 m, 07.VII.1997 (HMIM).– Kermanshah: Kermanshah, 31.V.1982 (HMIM); Kerend, Biranij, 26.VI.1968

(HMIM).– **Kordestan:** Divandareh, Saral, 2150 m, 04.III.1969 (HMIM); Sanandaj, Ariz, 2200 m, 05.VII.1972 (HMIM); Sarv Abad, Piazeh, 35°19'51"N 46°26'02"E, 2400–2630 m, 01.VII.2015 (COM).– **Esfahan:** Golpayegan, 17.VII.1949 (HMIM).– **Azerbaijan-e Sharghi:** Azizkandeh, 37°27'46"N 46°55'18"E, 1620 m, 21.VI.2015 (COM); Majarshin, pass 3km N, 37°44'17"N 46°09'20"E, 2220 m, 27.VI.2015 (COM); Nasir Abad, E, 37°15'19"N 47°16'22"E, 1690 m, 21.VI.2015 (COM).– **Azerbaijan-e Gharbi:** Ghooshchi, 20.VI.1970 (HMIM); Senji, 15.VI.1970 (HMIM); Rezaieh, Kuh-e Silvaneh, 24.VI.1970 (HMIM).– **Yazd:** Abarghoo, Aziz Abad, 25.VI.1972 (HMIM).

Remarks. This species was described from Lorestan. It is endemic to Iran.

Distribution. Northern, western and southwestern Iran.

Glaphyrus (s. str.) micans Faldermann, 1835

Material examined. Iran – **Mazandaran:** Mahmud Abad, 08.VI.1947 (HMIM).– **Tehran:** Evin; 08.1975 (HMIM); Varamin, 12.V.1949 (HMIM).– **Alborz:** Taleghan, 07.VII.2006 (COM), 05.VII.2011 (COM); Taleghan, Takieh, 30.VI.2007 (COM); Taleghan, Jahestan, 05.VII.2011 (COM).– **Azerbaijan-e Sharghi:** Maragheh, 3 km E, 37°24'37"N 46°18'10"E, 1740 m, 27.VI.2015 (COM); E Nasir Abad, 37°15'19"N 47°16'22"E, 1690 m, 21.VI.2015 (COM).– **Azerbaijan-e Gharbi:** 10 km S Makou, 10.VII (MNHN); Gheshlagh Pol, 36°06'12"N 46°20'54"E, 1475 m, 29.VI.2015 (COM).– **Esfahan:** Golpayegan, 17.VII.1949 (HMIM).– **Kermanshah:** Ghasr-e Shirin, 15.IV.1952 (HMIM), 13.V.1957 (HMIM).– **Yazd:** Tabas, 15.V.1949 (HMIM).– **Fars:** Firuz Abad, Dozghah, 10.IV.1951 (HMIM); 10 km W Persepolis (HMIM); Kazerun, V.1953 (HMIM).– **Ardabil:** Moghan, 07.VI.1958 (HMIM), 02.VI.1959 (HMIM).– **Kordestan:** Bijar, 10.VII.1968 (HMIM); Karim Abad, 24.VI.1949 (HMIM).– **Khuzestan:** Behbahan, 01.V.1968 (HMIM).

Distribution. Northwestern and southwestern Iran. Eastern Turkey, Iraq, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Syria.

Glaphyrus (s. str.) onopordi Reitter, 1903

Material examined. Iran – **Kerman:** Jiroft, 24.IV.1967 (HMIM), 26.IV.1974 (HMIM); Jiroft, Kharposht, 08.V.1969 (HMIM).– **Sistan va Baluchestan:** Zahedan, 29.VIII.1982 (HMIM);

Sarbaz, 24.IV.1950 (HMIM); Khash, 03.VIII.1968 (HMIM); 100 km N Iranshahr, 15.IV.1965 (MNHN).– **Khuzestan:** Behbahan, 28.IV.1969 (HMIM).– **Kohgiluyeh va Boyerahmad:** Dogonbadan, 11.V.1958 (HMIM).– **Ilam:** Mehran, 06.V.1947 (HMIM).

Distribution. Southern Iran. Iraq.

Glaphyrus (s. str.) oxypterus (Pallas, 1771)

Material examined. Iran – **Azerbaijan-e Sharghi:** Majarshin, pass 3km N, 37°44'17"N 46°09'20"E, 2220 m, 27.VI.2015 (COM); Nasir Abad, E, 37°15'19"N 47°16'22"E, 1690 m, 21.VI.2015 (COM).

Remarks. Modarres Awal (2006) recorded this species from Khorasan.

Distribution. Northwestern and northeastern Iran. Turkey, Central Asia.

Glaphyrus (s. str.) superbis ssp. *superbus* Champenois, 1898

Material examined. Iran – **Mazandaran:** Kuh-e Damavand, 14.VII.2006 (COM), 01.VII.2007 (COM), 22.VI.2008 (COM), 19.VI.2015 (COM), 23.VII.2015 (COM).– **Khorasan-e Shomali:** Estarkhi, 19.VI.2011 (COM); Kuh-e Shah Jahan, Sarparchin 18.VI.2011 (COM); Hesargalian, 19.VI.2011 (COM).– **Tehran:** Polur, 01.VII.2007 (COM), 22.VI.2008 (COM), 19.VI.2015 (COM); Damavand, 13.VII.1949 (HMIM); Damavand, Absard, 07.VII.1978 (HMIM).– **Alborz:** Taleghan, Takieh, 30.VI.2007 (COM); Taleghan, Mehran, 30.VI.2007 (COM).– **Esfahan:** Khonsar, 02.IV.1969 (HMIM), 30.VI.1969 (HMIM), 01-02.VII.1969 (HMIM); Golpayegan, Kuh-e Hendeh, 2200–2800 m, 27.VI.1967 (HMIM).

Remarks. Modarres Awal (2006) recorded the species from Khorasan.

Distribution. Northeastern Iran. Turkmenistan.

Glaphyrus (s. str.) superbis ssp. *straussi* Reitter, 1903

Material examined. Iran – **Azerbaijan-e Gharbi:** Ghoushchi, 20.VI.1970 (HMIM); Majarshin, pass 3km N, 37°44'17"N 46°09'20"E, 2220 m, 27.VI.2015 (COM).

Distribution. Northwestern Iran. Eastern Turkey.

Glaphyrus (s. str.) calvaster Zaitzev, 1923

Material examined. Iran – **Azerbaijan-e**

Gharbi: Makou, 08.VI.1971 (HMIM); Shapour, Akhte Khane (HMIM).

Distribution. Northwestern Iran (**first country record**). Armenia.

Discussion

Nikodým & Bezd k (2016) mentioned the following species, from Iran, in the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera: *Eulasia analis* (Solsky, 1876), *E. bocquilloni* (Zaitzev, 1923), *E. diadema* Reitter, 1890, *E. kordestana* Mitter, 2004, *E. genei* Truqui, 1848, *E. nitidinatis* Baraud, 1990, *E. papaveris* (Sturm, 1843), *E. persidis* Baraud, 1990, *E. pulchra* (Reitter, 1890), *E. speciosa* Champenois, 1900, *E. vittata lineata* (Faldermann, 1835), *E. zaitzevi* (Bogachev, 1947), *Pygopleurus basalis* (Reitter, 1890), *P. gordyenensis* (Petrovitz, 1971), *P. koniae* (Petrovitz, 1958), *P. immundus* (Reitter, 1903), *P. mardiensis* Baraud, 1989, *P. rapuzzii* Keith & Uliana, 2008, *P. rufovillosus* (Reitter, 1907), *P. tristis* (Petrovitz, 1968), *P. zagrosensis* Nikodým & Král, 1998, *Glaphyrus caucasicus* Kraatz, 1882, *G. cinnaberinus* Schweiger, 1949, *G. festivus* Ménétrés, 1836, *G. muticus* Reitter, 1903, *G. sequensi* Reitter, 1903, *G. varians* Ménétrés, 1836. The species *E. genei* was recently recorded from Iran (Uliana & Sabatinelli 2010). The occurrence of the other species in Iran is mostly based on the old citations, which appear to be doubtful and need confirmation. The record of *P. koniae* from Tehran (Baraud, 1990) is based on a single old specimen

(MNHN) that might be erroneously labeled. Thus this record requires confirmation. The record of *E. pulchra* from Iran was published before the description of its subspecies, *E. pulchra kurdistanica* which also includes the Iranian populations. We can consider the same for *E. vittata lineata* and its Iranian subspecies, *E. vittata persica*; and for *G. festivus* and *G. luristanus*: The report of *G. festivus* in Iran by Champenois (1903) refers certainly to *G. luristanus* which was described in the same year. *Glaphyrus caucasicus* is not cited from Iran by Nikodým & Keith (2007), neither *E. analis* and *E. diadema*, nor *P. gordyenensis*, *P. rufovillosus* and *P. tristis* by Baraud (1989, 1990), thus their citations in the Catalogue by Nikodým & Bezd k (2016) requires confirmation. In addition, Mitter (1990) considered *G. sequensi* a valid species but Nikodým & Keith (2007) treated *G. sequensi* as a synonym of *G. varians*. The identity of *G. cinnaberinus*, described from Iran, is unknown to Nikodým & Keith (2007) due to the type loss. *E. bocquilloni* and *E. zaitzevi*, both described from Iran, were unknown to Baraud (1989) and other specialists.

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